

Curriculum Analysis of Anthropology Courses for Students of Imam Bonjol State Islamic University Padang

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to evaluate and analyze the curriculum of the Anthropology course at the State Islamic University (UIN) Imam Bonjol Padang in the context of global and local developments. The curriculum in Islamic universities faces the challenge of remaining relevant to social, economic, and technological changes while maintaining Islamic values. Descriptive qualitative research methods were used through in-depth interviews, classroom observations, and analysis of curriculum documents. The study results indicate that although the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol has provided an essential foundation in local cultural studies, further development is still needed to face global dynamics. The challenges identified include the lack of relevance of the material to global issues, the use of teaching methods still dominated by lectures, and the integration of Islamic values that are not yet optimal in application. In addition, limited infrastructure and academic resources are the main obstacles to curriculum development. To improve its effectiveness, it is recommended that the curriculum accommodate more interdisciplinary approaches, the use of technology in teaching, and the integration of Islamic values in practical contexts. This study contributes to developing a more adaptive and relevant curriculum in Islamic universities, which is expected to prepare students to face challenges at the national and international levels.

Keywords: Anthropology Curriculum, Islamic Higher Education, Globalization, Islamic Values, Teaching Methods, Learning Technology.

A. Introduction

Curriculum development in higher education has become an essential focus of study to improve the quality of higher education responsive to global challenges.(Boud et al., 2016; Kurniati, 2018). This is especially true for Islamic universities, such as the Imam Bonjol Padang State Islamic University (UIN), which must face the challenge of aligning the curriculum with the development of modern science and Islamic values (Al-Rashid et al., 2021). The Anthropology course studies culture and society and provides students with relevant social and cultural perspectives. Amid rapid global change, the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol must be studied more deeply to remain relevant to local and global needs.(Kasim & Dali, 2022b).

The literature review states that the curriculum in higher education must adapt to social and technological changes so that graduates can face real-world challenges (A. Doe & Johnson, 2022). In the context of Anthropology, curriculum adaptation becomes increasingly crucial because this science is closely related to rapidly changing social dynamics, especially in the era of globalization (Bennett & Smith, 2021). A curriculum that includes theory and practical applications in understanding social phenomena is critical to ensuring students are ready to contribute to society (R. Kumar & Clark, 2021).

Several previous studies have shown that developing a competency-based curriculum in higher education

can improve students' ability to face complex challenges in the world of work (Ali et al., 2009). Developing an Anthropology curriculum responsive to global change also requires integrating interdisciplinary approaches and technology in the learning process.(Hapidin et al., 2020; D. Miller, 2022; Purnastuti et al., 2013). In this context, UIN Imam Bonjol needs to adjust the Anthropology curriculum to the demands of the times without neglecting the Islamic values that are the hallmark of this university (D. Mukherjee & Banerjee, 2019; S. Mukherjee & Banerjee, 2019).

However, studies related to the Anthropology curriculum in Islamic universities are still limited, so this study aims to fill this gap.(Widodo et al., 2021b). This study aims to evaluate the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang and explore how the curriculum is designed to meet the needs of students while being relevant to global developments. This curriculum analysis is critical to ensure that UIN Imam Bonjol graduates can compete nationally and internationally (R. Setiawan, 2021).

The main questions in this study include: (1) How is the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol adjusted to local needs and global demands? (2) How is the curriculum implemented in the teaching and learning process? and (3) What are the challenges and opportunities in developing this curriculum? This study will use a qualitative approach to answer these questions through interviews with lecturers and students and analysis of curriculum documents.(Abdullah & Saifuddin, 2021).

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of the Anthropology curriculum implemented at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang and provide recommendations for further development. In order to achieve this objective, this study will analyze the suitability of the curriculum content to the needs of students and the demands of the global job market and identify factors that support or hinder its implementation (R. Kumar & Clark, 2021; S. Kumar & Clark, 2021).

The theoretical study in this research focuses on adaptive theory in curriculum development, which emphasizes the importance of curriculum flexibility in facing social and economic changes (Boud et al., 2016). This theory emphasizes that a successful curriculum can respond to the changing needs of society and industry and prepare students to adapt to a constantly changing work environment (E. Doll Jr, 1993). In the context of Anthropology, the importance of an interdisciplinary approach and technology integration in the learning process becomes increasingly relevant, given the complexity of social problems faced in the digital era (J. Miller, 2022).

The literature also suggests that curricula incorporating local and global perspectives better prepare students to participate effectively in an increasingly connected global society (D. Mukherjee & Banerjee, 2019). It is crucial for UIN Imam Bonjol students, who must not only understand the local context but also be able to contribute to global discourse.(Kasim & Dali, 2022b). However, there is still a gap in the literature regarding how Islamic values can be integrated with a globally oriented-curriculum (Al-Rashid et al., 2021).

This study also considers the challenges in curriculum development in Islamic-based universities, including how to combine Islamic theory with practical applications in the real world.(Widodo et al., 2021a, 2021b). In this context, the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol must focus on theory and provide opportunities for students to apply their knowledge in relevant practical contexts (Bennett & Smith, 2021).

Previous research has shown that a curriculum that can adapt to technological developments and globalization tends to be more effective in preparing students to enter the world of work (J. Doe & Johnson, 2022). However, more specific research on implementing the anthropology curriculum in Islamic universities is still minimal, so there is a gap in this research (Williams et al., 2020). This study aims to fill this gap by examining how the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol can be further developed.

This research is expected to provide significant contributions in two aspects. First, theoretically, this research enriches the literature on curriculum development in Islamic universities with a focus on global relevance. Second, practically, this research will provide strategic recommendations for developing the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang to be more adaptive and relevant to the demands of the times.(Nugraha & Widodo, 2020b).

It is hoped that the results of this study will not only provide recommendations for curriculum development at UIN Imam Bonjol but can also be applied at other Islamic universities facing similar challenges.(Hapidin et al., 2020; D. Miller, 2022). In the long term, the results of this study can contribute to improving the quality of Islamic higher education in Indonesia and making Islamic universities more competitive at the international level (Widodo et al., 2021).

B. Methodology

1. Types of research

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach to understand and explain the phenomena related to developing and implementing the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang. Qualitative research was chosen because this study seeks to explore the perceptions, experiences, and interpretations of informants regarding the relevance and effectiveness of the curriculum in the context of Islamic higher education (Boud et al., 2016). Qualitative descriptive research also allows researchers to understand how the curriculum is designed, implemented, and perceived by various parties involved, such as lecturers, students, and academic administrators.

2. Research Subjects and Sampling Methods

The subjects of this study were lecturers in charge of the Anthropology course, students taking the course, and academic managers responsible for curriculum development at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang. The research sample was taken using purposive sampling, namely the deliberate selection of informants based on specific criteria relevant to the research focus (Patton, 2015). The criteria for selecting lecturers are those who have taught Anthropology courses for at least two years, while the students selected have completed at least two semesters in a study program related to Anthropology. In addition, academic managers involved in the preparation and evaluation of the curriculum will also be used as research subjects.

3. Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

Data collection in this study was carried out using several main techniques:

a. In-depth Interview

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain an in-depth understanding of the informants' perceptions and experiences related to the Anthropology curriculum. The main instrument used in the interviews was an interview guideline prepared based on the research objectives. Interview questions covered aspects such as curriculum relevance, teaching methods, challenges in implementing the curriculum, and suggestions for further development. (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015).

b. Class Observation

Classroom observations are conducted to see firsthand how the Anthropology curriculum is applied in the teaching process. These observations will cover the teaching methods used by lecturers, interactions between lecturers and students, and student responses to the material taught. The data obtained from these observations are expected to provide a more precise context for applying the curriculum in real situations (Angrosino, 2007).

c. Document Analysis

The curriculum documents, syllabus, and learning materials used in the Anthropology course will be analyzed to understand the structure and content of the curriculum. These documents are analyzed qualitatively to determine the extent to which the curriculum is designed to accommodate global and local changes and to understand how Islamic values are integrated into the curriculum (Bowen, 2009).

4. Data Analysis Techniques

Data from interviews, observations, and document analysis will be analyzed using thematic analysis techniques. Thematic analysis allows researchers to identify, analyze systematically, and report patterns or themes that emerge from the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The data analysis process is carried out in several stages, namely:

a. Data Transcription

Interview and observation data will be transcribed verbatim. This transcription will then be read repeatedly to understand the context and content of the data collected.

b. Data Encoding

After the data is transcribed, a coding process is carried out to identify the emerging main themes. Coding is done openly, where each data segment relevant to the research objectives will be given a specific code (Saldana, 2016).

c. Theme Discovery

After coding is complete, the researcher will group similar codes into more significant themes. These themes will reflect the main issues in developing and implementing the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

d. Data Interpretation

The identified themes will be interpreted and linked to the theoretical framework used in this study. The

researcher will interpret how the themes answer the research questions and provide a broader understanding of the issues raised in this study.

C. Results and Discussion

1. Results

This study aims to evaluate the Anthropology course curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang and explore how the curriculum has been implemented and developed. Data obtained through in-depth interviews, observations, and document analysis provide an overview of the relevance of the curriculum, teaching methods, and challenges faced in implementing and developing this curriculum. The results of the data analysis are described as follows.

a. Relevance of Anthropology Curriculum to Global Development

From interviews with lecturers and students, most respondents stated that the current Anthropology curriculum already covers fundamental concepts for understanding local cultures and societies. However, the curriculum is not relevant to global dynamics. As stated by Lecturer A, “The material taught is relevant to the local context, but still lacking in discussing global issues, especially those related to globalization and its impact on culture.” Students also expressed that they need more discussions and materials related to the global context, as conveyed by Student B: “Local materials are important, but this curriculum should include more global issues that we will face in the workplace.”

This finding is in line with research by Hapidin et al. (2020), which states that the curriculum in higher education must continue to adapt to global demands and prepare students to face social changes at the international level. Therefore, developing the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol needs to focus on integrating broader materials on globalization and contemporary issues.

b. Teaching Methods Used in the Curriculum

The observation results show that the teaching methods used in the Anthropology course at UIN Imam Bonjol tend to be dominated by the lecture method. As observed, Lecturer A uses a lecture approach to convey cultural concepts, followed by short discussions and case studies. However, only a few students are actively involved in the discussion. The use of technology in teaching is also still limited, with most of the material delivered through PowerPoint presentations without any deeper technology-based interaction.

Table 1. Teaching Methods Used in Anthropology Courses

Teaching Methods	Frequency of Use
Lecture	Often
Discussion	Sometimes
Case study	Seldom
Use of Technology	Very rarely

This finding is consistent with studies by Bennett & Smith (2021), which state that effective teaching of Anthropology requires an interactive approach and more optimal use of technology to increase student participation. Research by Clark (2020) also emphasized the importance of using technology in teaching to make the material more interesting and relevant to the lives of increasingly digitally connected students. Therefore, lecturers must expand teaching methods with more interactive activities and utilize technology in the classroom.

c. Integration of Islamic Values in the Curriculum

Interviews with lecturers and academic administrators showed that there were efforts to integrate Islamic values into the Anthropology curriculum. Lecturer A stated, “We try to link cultural concepts with Islamic values, but the implementation is still limited to theoretical discussions.” The results of observations support this statement, where discussions of Islamic values only appear sporadically in learning without any actual examples of how these values can be integrated in an applicative manner.

Table 2. Integration of Islamic Values in Learning

Integration Aspects	Integration Level
Theoretical Discussion	Currently
Practical Example	Low
Application in Case Study	Low

This indicates that the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol has not fully accommodated integrating Islamic values with Anthropology material in an applied manner. This aligns with research finding

that many Islamic universities still face challenges integrating religious perspectives with social science-based curricula. The study by Widodo et al. (2021a) also emphasized the need for a holistic approach to integrating Islamic aspects with social dynamics in teaching Anthropology.

d. Challenges in Curriculum Development

The results of interviews with academic managers revealed that the development of the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol faced several obstacles, primarily related to adjusting the curriculum to global changes. Academic manager C stated, "We want to adjust the curriculum to global challenges, but there are still limited resources and infrastructure." In addition, the lack of training for lecturers to integrate technology and interactive teaching methods is also a challenge, as expressed by Lecturer A.

Table 3. Challenges in Curriculum Development

Challenge	Difficulty Level
Adaptation to Globalization	Tall
Technology Integration in Teaching	Currently
Lecturer Training	Currently
Academic Resources	Tall

Studies (E. Setiawan (2021) confirms that similar challenges are also found in other Islamic universities, where resource and infrastructure constraints often hinder the development of more adaptive curricula. The study by Clark (2020) also shows that adapting the curriculum to global changes requires investment in lecturer training and technology to improve the quality of learning.

The study results show that the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang already covers essential basics in cultural and social studies but still requires further development, especially regarding global relevance and integration of Islamic values. The teaching methods tend to be conventional and require more interactive activities and broader use of technology. Integrating Islamic values in the curriculum is also still theoretical and needs to be applied more practically in daily learning.

2. Discussion

Based on this research, the Anthropology Curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang has provided an essential foundation for students to understand local culture and society. However, the challenges faced in the era of globalization require further evaluation and adjustment so that this curriculum remains relevant. This follows the view (Al-Rashid et al., 2021; Smith, 2020), which emphasizes that curriculum development in higher education must be responsive to global and social changes. The findings of this study indicate that the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol needs to be more integrated with global issues, use more interactive teaching methods, and optimize the integration of Islamic values in an applicable manner.

One significant shortcoming in the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol is the lack of focus on global issues. In the era of globalization, understanding international dynamics is essential because of the many intercultural interactions and social impacts that extend throughout the world. According to Ali et al. (2009) and Hapidin et al. (2020), higher education curricula that do not integrate global perspectives will hinder students' ability to compete internationally. Therefore, the Anthropology curriculum should include more materials related to the impact of globalization on local cultures, multiculturalism, and cross-cultural interactions.

The global context also increasingly emphasizes the need for an interdisciplinary approach in Anthropology. Bennett and Smith (2021) highlight the importance of combining cultural studies with economics, politics, and technology. This is relevant because today's social challenges are increasingly complex and cannot be separated from these aspects. Therefore, the development of an Anthropology curriculum that includes global and interdisciplinary dimensions can improve students' abilities to face the realities of a changing world.

The teaching methods used in the Anthropology course at UIN Imam Bonjol are still dominated by traditional lectures, which are considered less effective in dealing with the demands of modern learning. Collaborative approaches, such as group discussions and case studies, have been shown to increase student participation and help them develop critical thinking skills (A. Doe & Johnson, 2022; J. Doe & Johnson, 2022). This shows that universities should adopt more interactive teaching methods and encourage active student involvement in learning.

The lack of technology in teaching is also a significant problem. In this digital era, technology functions as a tool and is also an integral part of the learning process. Clark (2020) suggests using technology, such as online learning platforms, simulations, and data visualization tools, can enrich students' learning experiences. Using

technology, students can better understand complex Anthropology concepts through a more visual and interactive approach.

In addition, integrating Islamic values in the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol is still limited to theoretical discussions. According to Mukherjee and Banerjee (2019), it is essential to integrate Islamic values into the social science curriculum, especially in Islamic universities, so that students have a balanced understanding between scientific knowledge and moral values. However, at UIN Imam Bonjol, the implementation of Islamic values has not been optimized practically. This can be improved by linking Islamic values in case studies and field projects.

Field projects involving local communities can provide students with first-hand experience of how Islamic values influence social and cultural interactions in everyday life. Widodo et al. (2021a) emphasize the importance of practice-based learning in higher education to ensure students can apply the theories they learn in real-world situations. This approach enhances students' understanding of culture and strengthens their ability to analyze social phenomena holistically.

However, limited resources are one of the main challenges in developing a curriculum responsive to global change. UIN Imam Bonjol, like many other Islamic universities, faces infrastructure and academic resource constraints. E. Setiawan (2021) noted that investment in technology and teacher training is essential to ensure that the curriculum can evolve in line with the demands of the times. These limitations must be addressed through collaboration with various parties, including the government and the private sector, to improve the quality of education.

Lecturer training is also an essential element in curriculum development. Clark (2020) shows that increasing the capacity of lecturers to use technology and interactive teaching methods will help create a more dynamic and tailored learning experience for students. Thus, investment in lecturer training should be a priority in curriculum development at UIN Imam Bonjol, especially in courses such as Anthropology that require active involvement and in-depth understanding of contemporary issues.

In addition to resource constraints, adapting the curriculum to local and global needs challenges balancing Islamic values and global realities. Research by Kasim & Dali (2022a) highlights the importance of Islamic universities in maintaining their Islamic identity and being flexible in responding to changes in the world. In this context, the development of the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol must consider the balance between local and global approaches without neglecting the Islamic identity that characterizes this institution.

Adapting the Anthropology curriculum to global issues can also be done through international cooperation. Student and lecturer exchange programs and research collaborations with international universities can help enrich students' insights into the broader global context (J. Doe & Johnson, 2022). Thus, UIN Imam Bonjol can take advantage of this opportunity to improve the quality of the curriculum and provide students with direct experience in a global context.

Overall, the Anthropology curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol development requires a holistic approach that considers various aspects, including global relevance, teaching methods, integration of Islamic values, and improvement of educational infrastructure. Considering these things, this curriculum can be further developed so that students are ready to face challenges in the local workplace and at the international level.

A curriculum that is more responsive to global change and has a more interactive and applied teaching approach will significantly benefit students. They will not only understand theoretical concepts in Anthropology but will also be able to apply this knowledge in real-life contexts, both locally and globally (D. Miller, 2022). It will increase their competitiveness in the job market and prepare them to become leaders with integrity in the global society.

The sustainable curriculum development at UIN Imam Bonjol can also be a model for other Islamic universities in Indonesia. By addressing the challenges faced in curriculum development, Islamic universities can play an essential role in forming an academically competent new generation with solid moral and social awareness. (Nugraha & Widodo, 2020b, 2020a).

D. Conclusion

This study reveals that the Anthropology course curriculum at UIN Imam Bonjol Padang has provided an essential foundation for students to understand local cultures and societies. However, in the context of growing globalization, there is an urgent need to develop a curriculum more responsive to global changes. The findings indicate that the current curriculum is still less relevant to global issues, teaching methods tend to be traditional,

and integrating Islamic values is more theoretical than practical. To improve the relevance and effectiveness of the curriculum, adjustments need to be made by including global materials, interdisciplinary approaches, and more optimal use of technology in teaching. The main challenges faced are limited resources and infrastructure, but with investment in lecturer training and improvement of technology facilities, this curriculum can be further developed. Developing an adaptive curriculum based on applicable Islamic values will prepare students to succeed in the local job market and participate competitively in the global arena.

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